

Valuable data and applications eventually need industrial-strength infrastructure. Will NoSQL data stores get there? (A position? Paper)

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The promise of better scalability and availability [Vogels 2008] encourages application developers to forgo rich transactional semantics and deploy on NoSQL (non-transactional) datastores (DS). There is also a renewed realization that many applications do not need full transactional support a la ACID. These observations are often followed by the conclusion that traditional industrial-strength databases (i.e., full-fledged RDBMSs) will be replaced by DSs. For DSs to succeed, however, the community must incorporate the deeper lessons of building data management infrastructure and applications. Not providing transactional support is fine, but there are other virtues of RDBMSs that explain their broad adoption. Two areas deserve more attention in the design and use of DSs: what RDBMSs offer besides transactions, and what applications need from the infrastructure. As the applications and data on DSs become more valuable, it will no longer be enough to just be fast, cheap, and scalable.

Much research [Jajodia 1997] was devoted to the relaxation of ACID to better support applications, an early indication of the limitations of ACID. In practice, such applications end up deployed on RDBMSs “in spite of” ACID, utilizing other virtues of RDBMSs. For example, RDBMSs integrally support security, including rich access control; auditability of end-user and administrator operations. RDBMSs also provide recovery at the level of the entities the application cares about, rather than for raw bits on storage; and more broadly fairly transparent high availability and scalability. For data considered valuable, RDBMSs are the best packaged, most complete software artifact available. DSs must strive for such integration while maintaining their virtues of simplicity, scalability, etc.; this may result in an multiplicity of solutions as one size does not fit all, but is no excuse for less than industrial-strength.

The current trend is to develop applications from the APIs/building blocks provided by NoSQL DSs. However, those building blocks are defined by the needs and capabilities of the DS infrastructure, not the applications. This leaves a lot of heavy lifting to the application even when transactions are not needed, including functionality that is best achieved as an integral part of the infrastructure. As examples, fault tolerance and scalability can be and are often addressed ad-hoc in each application, building them on DSs. In the long run this an infeasible approach except for the most exotic problems and the few organizations with nearly infinite resources. Bridging the semantic gap between the needs of the application and the capabilities of the infrastructure requires approaching the gap from both ends.

[Jajodia 1997] S. Jajodia, L. Kerschberg (Eds.): Advanced Transaction Models and Architectures. Kluwer 1997.

[Vogels 2008] W. Vogels; Eventually Consistent. ACM Queue, <http://queue.acm.org/detail.cfm?id=1466448>, December 2008.

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